

Two New Saponins from the Root of *Amaranthus spinosus* Linn*

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Manuscript received 21 March 1979, accepted 4 March 1980

Phytochemical investigation on the root of *Amaranthus spinosus* Linn. revealed the presence of two new saponins (I and II). Structure of saponins I and II were assigned to be as β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 2)- β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 2)- β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3)- α -spinasterol and β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3)- α -spinasterol respectively.

AMARANTHUS spinosus Linn is an erect herb. Roots of the plant is reported^{1,2} to be used in menorrhagia, gonorrhoea, eczema, colic and as a lactagogue. Isolation of α -spinasterol, α -spinasterol-octacosanoate and a new saponin of oleanolic acid from this plant have already been reported^{3,4}. Dried and powdered roots of the plant was extracted successively with pet ether (60-80)°, CHCl_3 and MeOH. The MeOH extract was reduced to smaller volume and kept in a freeze overnight, shining crystals of KNO_3 was filtered out and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. From this portion two saponins (I and II) were isolated in pure form by using different chromatographic technique. In this paper structure elucidation of these two saponins are described.

Two new saponins (I and II) were crystallised from MeOH- CHCl_3 (2 : 1), m.p. 340°(d), $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 51.1^\circ$ (pyridine) and m.p. 290°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 40.1^\circ$ (pyridine) and analysed for $\text{C}_{47}\text{H}_{88}\text{O}_{16}$ and $\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{78}\text{O}_{11}$ for saponins (I and II) respectively.

On complete acid hydrolysis with 7% H_2SO_4 the saponins yielded α -spinasterol, D-glucose and an artefact formed during acid hydrolysis which was identified as stigma-8(14), 22-dien-3 β -ol⁵. Due to the formation of this compd., it was not possible to find out the molar ratios of aglycone : sugar present in these saponins by the method of complete acid hydrolysis. In order to calculate the molar ratios, a controlled method of hydrolysis was developed by using 0.02 N- H_2SO_4 for 45 minutes. Both the saponins, on controlled acid hydrolysis yielded α -spinasterol- β -D-glucopyranoside⁶ and D-glucose in the molar ratio of 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 respectively.

The α -spinasterol- β -D-glucoside, $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{58}\text{O}_6$, have ($M^+ 574$), m.p. 284-86°, tetraacetate, m.p.

156-58°. Moreover, the MS of both the free glycoside and its tetraacetate showed fairly stable molecular ions and the spectrum of the acetate distinctly showing characteristic fragmentation of Δ^{22} -steroids and hexapyranoside tetraacetate. Also, the NMR spectrum (60 MHz) of the tetraacetate showed the signal for C-5 sugar proton at $\delta 3.62$, considerably upfield from that of methyl- α -D-glucose tetraacetate⁷. The sugar linkage of this glucoside was thus assigned the β -configuration, since the C-5 proton signal in β -glucosides is known⁸ to be shifted upfield from that in α -anomers and its remains unaffected⁹ by the nature of the aglycone.

The saponins were completely methylated by Hakomori's method. Complete methylations were confirmed by IR spectra of the permethylated products. The permethylated saponin I on complete hydrolysis yielded 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-*O*-methyl- β -D-glucose, m.p. 93-94°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 83.2^\circ$ (H_2O) (Lit.¹¹, m.p. 96°, $[\alpha]_D + 84^\circ$) and 3, 4, 6-tri-*O*-methyl- β -D-glucose, m.p. 96-98°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 79.2^\circ$ (H_2O) (Lit.¹², m.p. 97-98° $[\alpha]_D + 78.1^\circ$) in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The permethylated saponin II on hydrolysis yielded 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2, 3, 6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose m.p. 120-121° $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 69.1^\circ$ (H_2O) (Lit.¹³, m.p. 121-123°, $[\alpha]_D + 70^\circ$) in the molar ratio of 1 : 1. Periodate oxidation of the saponins was carried out at room temperature using 0.1M sodium metaperiodate solution. Consumption of oxidant and liberation of formic acid were found to be 4.12 and 0.98 moles respectively for saponin I and 3.2 and 1.02 moles respectively for saponin II.

With regard to the configuration of saponin glycosidic linkages, it is a general observation that D-sugars occur with β -glycosidic and L-sugars with α -glycosidic linkages¹⁴. The calculation of molar rotation of the saponins on the basis of Klyne's rule¹⁵ also supports the β -linkages. The calculated

* Presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, held at Andhra University, Waltair, India (Dec. 1978)

TABLE 1—MOLECULAR ROTATION CALCULATION OF SAPONIN I AND II

Compound	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$
	Lit. Value	
Methyl- β -D-glucopyranoside	-34.2°	-66°
	Observed value	
α -Spinasterol- β -D-glucopyranoside	-35°	-200.1°
	Calculated value	
For Saponin I	—	-332°
For Saponin II	—	-266°
	Observed value	
For Saponin I	51.1°	-463°
For Saponin II	40.1°	-299°

$[M]_D$ of saponin I and saponin II (Table 1) were -332° and -266° respectively which are in reasonable agreement with the observed value -463° and -299° respectively. Hence the structures of saponin I and saponin II can be represented as follows :

Experimental

All specific rotations are equilibrium values. All evaporations were carried out in vacuum at 35-40°. Whatman No. 1 paper was used for analytical paper chromatography and Whatman No. 3 MM paper for preparative chromatography.

The solvent mixture (v/v) used for partition chromatography of sugars were: A, *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5); upper layer; B, *n*-butanol : pyridine : water (6 : 4 : 3); C, ethyl acetate : pyridine : water (8 : 2 : 1). Spray reagents were (a) aqueous saturated aniline oxalate and (b) alkaline silver nitrate solution.

Isolation of Saponin (I and II) :

Dried and powdered root (5 kg) of the plant was extracted successively with petroleum ether (60-80°), CHCl_3 and MeOH. The methanol extract of the roots was reduced to a smaller volume, and

kept in a freeze overnight. Shining crystal of KNO_3 was filtered out and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. The brown solid obtained gave positive test for saponins when shaken with water. The material was dissolved in *n*-butanol and acetone was added to this solution when a brown precipitate was obtained. The pale-yellow amorphous powder was isolated by centrifugation. The powder was resolved in three components by TLC on a silica gel G plate using a solvent system prepared by addition of MeOH to a mixture of 2 ml H_2O and 30 ml CHCl_3 till the whole was clear. The mixture was chromatographed on a silica gel column and saponins (I and II) were eluted with MeOH : CHCl_3 = 10 : 90 and 8 : 92 respectively. The pure saponins (I and II) were crystallised from CHCl_3 : MeOH mixture having m.p. 304°(d), $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 51.1^\circ$ (c, 1 in pyridine) for saponin I and m.p. 290°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 40.1^\circ$ (C, 1.5 in pyridine) for saponin II and analysed for $\text{C}_{47}\text{H}_{88}\text{O}_{16}$ and $\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{78}\text{O}_{11}$ for saponins (I and II) respectively.

Identification of Aglycone and Sugars :

Hydrolysis of saponins I and II with 7% H_2SO_4 yielded α -spinasterol, m. p. 168-70°, $[\alpha]_D^{27} - 3.8^\circ$ (CHCl_3). Superimposable IR spectra and mixed melting point suggested its identity with α -spinasterol. Stigmasta-8 (14), 22-dien-3 β -ol, obtained by acid hydrolysis, separated from α -spinasterol by chromatography of the acetate over AgNO_3 (15%) impregnated silica gel. Stigmasta-8(14), 22-dien-3 β -yl acetate was crystallised from MeOH m.p. 136-37°, $[\alpha]_D^{27} - 42^\circ$ (CHCl_3); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 1730, 1250(OAC),

$970 \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{C} = \text{C} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{H} \end{array} \right) \text{cm}^{-1}$. MS : *m/e* (rel. intensity 454

(M^+ , 8), 49(2), 411(2), 394(79), 379(8), 351(12), 342(2), 313(25), 282(12), 273(4), 255(62), 228(12), 213(16), NMR: (δ in CDCl_3) 0.78(18-Me), 0.91(19-Me), 1.08d(21-Me), 0.86-1.08 m (25-Me, 26-Me, 29-Me), 2.08(OAC), 4.73 m (H-3), 5.30m (H-22, H-23). (Found : C, 82.20, H, 11.35. Calc. for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$: C 81.93, H, 11.01%). The sugars in aqueous portion were identified as D-glucose by paper chromatography (solvent systems A, B and C).

Partial Hydrolysis of Saponins I and II :

200 mg of each of the saponins was hydrolysed with 0.02N Na_2SO_4 (50 ml) for 45 minutes. Both the saponins yielded α -spinasterol- β -D-glucopyranoside and D-glucose. Gravimetric estimation of α -spinasterol- β -D-glucoside and spectrophotometric estimation of D-glucose, showed the molar ratio of glucoside : glucose 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 in saponins I and II respectively. α -Spinasterol- β -D-glucoside were crystallised from C_6H_6 - EtOH, m.p. 284-86°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 35^\circ$ (pyridine); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 320(OH) 970 cm^{-1} , MS : *m/e* (rel.intensity) 574 ($\text{M}^+1.3$), 559 (0.3), 556(0.1),

531(0.3), 433(4), 412(16), 394(40), 379(10), 369(6), 351(12), 300(10), 2.9(9), 273(15), 271(43), 255(65), 253(32) and 55(100) (Found : C, 72.0 : H, 10.5, Calc. for $C_{35}H_{58}O_6$: C, 73.1, H, 10.1%.

Permethylation of Saponins I and II :

50% NaH dispersion in oil (ca. 250 mg) was suspended in DMSO (25 ml) and kept in an oil bath at 80° for 1 hr. A solution of saponins (150 mg) in DMSO (5 ml) was then added gradually and the mixture was kept at 80° for 1 hr with constant stirring. It was cooled in ice and MeI (3 ml) was added in drops. The fully methylated product isolated in the usual way showed no absorption band in the region of 3500-3600 cm^{-1} in IR. The permethylated saponin I on complete acid hydrolysis with $N-H_2SO_4$ yielded 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-*o*-methyl- β -D-glucose m.p. 93-94°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 83.2^\circ$ (H_2O) and 3, 4, 6-tri-*o*-methyl-D-glucose, m.p. 96-98°, $[\alpha]_D^{27} + 79.2^\circ$ (H_2O) in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The permethylated saponin II on acid hydrolysis in the same way, yielded 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-*o*-methyl-D-glucose and 2, 3, 6-tri-*o*-methyl-D-glucose, m.p. 120-21°, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 69.1^\circ$ (H_2O) in 1 : 1 molar ratio. Molar ratio of the methylated sugars was determined by alkaline hypiodite method¹⁶.

Periodate-oxidation studies on saponin I and saponin II were carried out with 0.1M sodium metaperiodate solution. Consumption of the oxidant was determined spectrophotometrically¹⁷ and was found to be 4.12 and 3.2 moles for saponins I and II respectively. The liberation of formic acid were estimated in the usual way¹⁸ and were found to be 0.98 and 1.02 moles for saponins I and II respectively.

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